

PATHOGENETIC SUBSTANTIATION AND OPTIMIZATION OF TREATMENT OF INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT PATHOLOGY

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Abstract: The article analyzes the pathogenetic mechanisms linking inflammatory periodontal diseases and gastrointestinal tract disorders. The influence of microbiome imbalance, cytokine dysregulation, and systemic inflammation on periodontal tissues is discussed. Particular attention is given to the use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) in this patient category. The rationale for using local NSAID formulations (gels, applications, mouth rinses) as a promising approach to reducing inflammation and minimizing gastrointestinal side effects is provided. The prospects of combination therapy involving gastroprotectors, probiotics, and herbal components are highlighted.

Keywords: inflammatory periodontal diseases, gastrointestinal tract, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, local application, NSAIDs, gastropathy, combination therapy.

Introduction

Inflammatory periodontal diseases (gingivitis, periodontitis) occupy a leading position among dental pathologies detected in the population of different age groups. These conditions are complex polyethological processes based on a violation of the balance of the oral microbiota and immune-inflammatory reactions of the body. Periodontal damage is accompanied by destruction of connective tissue structures, resorption of the alveolar bone and weakening of the ligamentous apparatus of the teeth, which can lead to their mobility and subsequent loss.

Inflammatory periodontal diseases acquire special clinical significance in patients with concomitant pathology of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT), which is observed in 60-70% of the adult population Borovsky E.V. (2020)[1]. Gastrointestinal diseases (gastritis, peptic ulcer, gastroesophageal reflux disease, intestinal dysbiosis, irritable bowel syndrome) have a pronounced effect on the condition of the oral cavity, contributing to the chronization of inflammatory

processes in periodontal tissues, changes in salivation, impaired acid-base balance and microbial biocenosis [2,3].

In patients with gastrointestinal diseases, especially with impaired gastric acid and dysbiosis, there is a decrease in the buffer capacity of saliva, a decrease in its bactericidal activity, which creates favorable conditions for the reproduction of pathogenic microflora. The most important role is played by dysbiotic disruption of the composition of bacterial communities, both in the gastrointestinal tract and in the oral cavity, which leads to active colonization of periodontal pockets by bacteria of the "red complex" (*Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Tannerella forsythia*, *Treponema denticola*), producing proteolytic enzymes, toxins and lipopolysaccharides. This, in turn, initiates the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-1b (IL-1b), interleukin-6 (IL-6), tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), activates osteoclastic bone resorption and supports chronic inflammation in periodontal [4, 5].

Given the pronounced effect of gastrointestinal diseases on the course of inflammatory periodontal diseases, the development of integrated approaches to the treatment of this group of patients is of particular importance. Optimization of the therapeutic strategy requires not only suppression of local inflammatory processes in periodontitis, but also simultaneous correction of gastrointestinal pathologies [6].

The use of anti-inflammatory drugs, in particular, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), which have analgesic, decongestant effects and the ability to modulate cytokine activity, is considered as one of the promising areas. However, the appointment of NSAIDs in patients with concomitant gastrointestinal pathology is associated with the risk of developing gastropathies and other complications, which requires careful selection of drugs, their dosage, duration of use, as well as the use of drugs with gastroprotective properties.

This review is devoted to the analysis of current data on pathogenetic links between inflammatory periodontal diseases and diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, as well as optimization of approaches to the treatment of this category of patients. Special attention is paid to the use of anti-inflammatory drugs, including NSAIDs, as a component of complex therapy aimed at reducing the activity of inflammatory processes, protecting periodontal tissues and preventing complications from the hard structures of teeth.

THE USE OF NONSTEROIDAL ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUGS IN INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH

GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT PATHOLOGY: THEIR EFFECTIVENESS, DOSAGES AND THERAPEUTIC EFFECTS

The use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) in the treatment of inflammatory periodontal diseases is actively being investigated in dentistry, however, the safety and effectiveness of this group of drugs in patients with gastrointestinal (GI) pathology require special attention. This category of patients has an increased risk of developing gastropathies, erosive and ulcerative lesions of the gastric and intestinal mucosa against the background of systemic NSAID use. Nevertheless, clinical studies demonstrate that the proper use of NSAIDs in small doses or in combination with gastroprotectors can have a pronounced anti-inflammatory effect, contributing to the stabilization of periodontal disease.

Discussion

The use of NSAIDs in patients with inflammatory periodontal diseases and concomitant gastrointestinal pathology has significant therapeutic potential. However, the appointment of this group of drugs requires a special approach:

- The use of gastroprotectors in the systemic use of NSAIDs.
- Preference for selective COX-2 inhibitors (celecoxib) in patients with peptic ulcer disease.
- Expanding the practice of topical NSAID use (gels, applications) as a safe and effective alternative to systemic therapy.

The inclusion of NSAIDs in the complex therapy of inflammatory periodontal diseases in patients with gastrointestinal pathology contributes not only to reducing inflammatory processes, but also to improving the quality of life of patients, minimizing the risk of complications from the gastrointestinal tract.

ANALYSIS OF DATA FROM CLINICAL STUDIES ON THE USE OF NSAIDS IN THE TREATMENT OF INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT PATHOLOGY

To date, the role of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) as modulators of inflammatory reactions in patients with inflammatory periodontal diseases is increasingly being discussed in the literature. However, the use of this group of drugs in people with concomitant diseases of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT), including chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer, gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) and intestinal dysbiosis, is particularly difficult.

A key limitation of the widespread use of NSAIDs in patients with gastrointestinal diseases is the risk of developing gastropathies, erosive and

ulcerative lesions, and gastrointestinal bleeding, which is especially important for elderly patients and people with a long history of gastroenterological diseases.

Despite this, clinical research data indicate that with proper selection of dosages, forms of administration and concomitant gastroprotection, the use of NSAIDs can be an effective component of complex therapy of inflammatory periodontal diseases, improving the clinical and biochemical parameters of periodontal tissue.

Modern research highlights the importance of topical use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) in the treatment of inflammatory periodontal diseases, especially in patients with concomitant diseases of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT). Since the systemic use of NSAIDs is associated with the risk of erosive and ulcerative lesions of the gastric and duodenal mucosa, the use of topical forms of drugs allows to achieve a therapeutic effect, minimizing undesirable side effects.

Topical use of NSAIDs in patients with inflammatory periodontal diseases and concomitant gastrointestinal pathologies is a promising area of complex therapy. It allows achieving significant improvements in clinical parameters, such as reducing the depth of periodontal pockets, reducing the bleeding index, restoring clinical attachment, while reducing the risk of developing gastropathies and other systemic complications. Further study of combined regimens, including local forms of NSAIDs, antiseptics and herbal components, is important for the development of personalized approaches to the treatment of patients with combined pathology of the oral cavity and digestive organs.

Prospects for further research:

1. Development of personalized treatment regimens. A promising direction is to create differentiated schemes for the use of NSAIDs in patients with inflammatory periodontal diseases, taking into account individual characteristics, including the nature of gastroenterological pathology, age, and severity of periodontitis. Special attention should be paid to the selection of drugs, taking into account their selectivity for COX-1 and COX-2, as well as a combination of systemic and local forms.

2. Long-term monitoring of the condition of periodontal and gastrointestinal tissues. Long-term (from 6 months or more) prospective studies will allow an objective assessment of the effect of NSAIDs on the stability of remission of inflammatory periodontal diseases, the dynamics of bone

resorption and regeneration, as well as the incidence of gastropathies and exacerbations of gastrointestinal diseases.

3. Study of the potential of local forms of selective COX-2 inhibitors. The creation and clinical testing of topical gels, films, and mouthwashes based on celecoxib and meloxicam may become a safe alternative to systemic therapy, especially in patients with peptic ulcer, gastritis, or GERD. Assessment of bioavailability, the depth of penetration of active substances into periodontal tissues and the duration of their action will optimize treatment regimens.

4. Combination of NSAIDs with gastroprotectors and probiotics

Conducting randomized controlled trials to study the effectiveness of the combined use of NSAIDs and proton pump inhibitors (omeprazole, pantoprazole), as well as drugs that normalize the intestinal microbiota (probiotics), will help reduce the risk of systemic complications and improve treatment outcomes.

5. The role of natural ingredients in adjuvant therapy. Further study of the potential of plant extracts (ginger, linseed oil, curcumin) with anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and membrane-stabilizing properties remains relevant. Their inclusion in topical preparations or use in combination with low-dose NSAIDs may enhance the therapeutic effect and reduce adverse reactions.

6. Focus on restoring the microbiome of the oral cavity and intestines. Recent studies have revealed a close relationship between dysbiotic changes in the microbiota of the gastrointestinal tract and the composition of the microbial communities of periodontal pockets. A promising direction is to evaluate the effect of local forms of NSAIDs on the microbiocenosis of the oral cavity, as well as the possibility of a synergistic effect when combined with probiotics and antiseptics.

Conclusion.

The analysis of modern data indicates the existence of a complex pathogenetic relationship between inflammatory periodontal diseases and pathology of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT). Violations of the biocenosis of the oral cavity, dysbiotic changes in the intestinal microflora, systemic inflammation, acidic conditions of the stomach and impaired barrier function of the mucous membranes create conditions for the chronization of the inflammatory process in periodontal tissues and the acceleration of destructive changes in bone tissue.

The use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) in the treatment of inflammatory periodontal diseases demonstrates high clinical

efficacy, expressed in reducing bleeding, reducing the depth of periodontal pockets, improving clinical attachment and stabilizing destructive processes in the alveolar bone. However, the systemic use of NSAIDs in patients with chronic gastrointestinal diseases (gastritis, peptic ulcer, gastroesophageal reflux disease, intestinal dysbiosis) is associated with the risk of gastropathies, erosive lesions of the mucous membrane and bleeding, which limits the long-term use of this group of drugs.

In this regard, the development and implementation of local forms of NSAIDs (gels, applications, therapeutic films, rinsing solutions) is of particular importance, which make it possible to act directly on the inflammatory focus, achieving a high concentration of active substances in periodontal tissues, with minimal systemic effects and reducing the risk of side effects from the gastrointestinal tract.

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